

Quanti Farm

**CROP & LIVESTOCK FARMING DATAS
INTEGRATED MONITORING
& GUIDANCE SYSTEMS**

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FACTSHEET #9

WHAT ARE THE DATSs?

Digital Agricultural Technology Solutions (DATSs) are digital tools, systems, and platforms that collect, analyse, and use data to improve **farm management, productivity, sustainability, and animal welfare.**

They support better decision-making by transforming **real-time and historical data into targeted, actionable insights** for farmers and advisors.

WHAT ARE CROP & LIVESTOCK FARMING DATSs?

Crop & Livestock Farming DATSs are digital solutions that support both **crop production and animal production systems**.

They help farmers monitor fields, crops, animals, and environmental conditions, enabling **more precise, timely, and informed management decisions** across the whole farm.

By integrating data from different sources, such as sensors, machinery, weather information, and digital records, these DATSs support **efficient resource use, improved productivity, and sustainable farm practices** in mixed or specialised farming systems.

WHO IS IT FOR?

Crop & Livestock Farming DATSs are designed for:

Farmers and Farm Managers
operating crop, livestock,
or mixed farming systems

Advisers and Extension Services
supporting data-driven
farm management

Agricultural Consultants and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)
promoting digital solutions

Researchers and Stakeholders
analysing digitalisation
in crop and livestock farming

They are applicable across **different farm sizes, production systems, and geographic contexts.**

KEY OBJECTIVES

To support better farm management decisions through data-driven insights

To increase productivity and efficiency in crop and livestock systems

To reduce input use, costs, and operational risks

To improve environmental sustainability, soil health and animal welfare

To enable evidence-based and targeted crop management practices

MAIN FEATURES

Crop & Livestock Farming DATSs include a range of digital technologies that support observation, guidance, and management across the farm:

Recording & Mapping Technologies (RMT)

Purpose: Observe and map what is happening in fields and on the farm.

Soil sensors

Devices placed in the ground that provide information on soil conditions.

Satellite and UAV imagery

Use satellite and drone images to detect crop stress and areas of concern.

Yield mapping tools

Show which parts of a field produce more or less yield.

Weather stations

Monitor rainfall, temperature, wind, and other weather parameters at the farm level.

MAIN FEATURES

Guidance / Controlled Traffic Farming (CTF)

Purpose: Guide machinery precisely and protect soil.

GPS auto-steering

Helps tractors drive accurately, saving time and fuel.

RTK guidance

Provides high-precision positioning for farm machinery.

Traffic lane planning systems

Define optimal machinery paths to reduce soil compaction.

Together, these technologies help farmers **monitor conditions, manage operations more precisely, and optimise both crop and livestock production**, supporting sustainable and efficient whole-farm management.

Learn
More

quantifarm.eu
info@quantifarm.eu

Contact _____

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